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Technology, Democracy, And Election Credibility: An Appraisal Of E-Governance In Nigeria's 2023 Presidential Polls In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This paper examined the role of e-governance technologies in enhancing democratic credibility during Nigeria's 2023 presidential election in Rivers State. Anchored on Rogers' Diffusion of Innovation Theory, the paper assessed how innovations such as the Bimodal Voter Accreditation System (BVAS) and the INEC Result Viewing (IReV) portal were adopted to address electoral fraud, improve transparency, and promote voter participation. Findings revealed that while these innovations signaled progress, their diffusion was hindered by technical malfunctions, weak institutional capacity, and entrenched distrust in political processes. The study concludes that technology alone cannot resolve structural governance challenges but must be integrated into a broader framework of institutional reforms, inclusivity, and citizen engagement. Recommendations include strengthening electoral infrastructure, safeguarding INEC's independence, broadening political inclusiveness, and intensifying civic education. Overall, the study highlights that successful diffusion of electoral innovations requires not only technological adoption but also legitimacy, accountability, and trust in governance.

Keywords: BVAS, e-governance, election management, democratic legitimacy, Diffusion of Innovation Theory, IReV

INTRODUCTION

The quality of public service delivery is widely regarded as a fundamental measure of the welfare and well-being of citizens. In many developing countries, the effectiveness of government institutions is directly tied to how efficiently services are provided to the people. In Nigeria, however, public service delivery has long been associated with inefficiency, corruption, and poor outcomes (Abati, 2023). A recent study by Oladipupo (2023) identified a striking gap between citizens' expectations of service delivery and the actual quality of services rendered by public servants. This disjuncture has become a major concern for governance and development in the country. To ensure that public sector agencies effectively implement government policies, it is crucial to investigate the role of e-governance in improving service delivery. This focus is particularly important because Nigeria's public service has consistently been associated with poor service culture, limited employee engagement, and negative customer experiences, all of which undermine the credibility and functionality of government institutions. In response to these challenges, Nigeria has gradually begun to adopt e-governance initiatives across sectors. Attempts by the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) to conduct free, fair, and

credible elections provide a notable example of how technology has been deployed to address long-standing governance deficits (Egobueze & Nwaoburu, 2025). Elections are vital to democracy as they provide citizens with the opportunity to choose their leaders and influence governance. They serve as a mechanism for political accountability, ensuring that those in power remain responsive to the people's needs. Nwaoburu and Egobueze, (2024) argue that through elections, legitimacy is conferred on governments, reducing the likelihood of political instability. They also promote inclusiveness by allowing diverse voices and interests to be represented in decision-making. Furthermore, elections strengthen the rule of law and civic participation, fostering a culture of political engagement. Ultimately, credible elections are essential for trust, transparency, and the consolidation of democratic governance.

Electoral reforms in Nigeria have often been incremental, but each election cycle has witnessed innovations aimed at strengthening transparency and credibility. For instance, prior to 2015, INEC relied on the Automated Fingerprints Identification System (AFIS) and Direct Data Capture (DDC) machines (Adoki, Davies & Egobueze, 2023). However, in 2015, the Commission introduced smart card readers to electronically authenticate voters, marking the first time in Nigeria's electoral history that such technology was deployed nationwide. This shift represented a milestone in the modernization of election management and aligned Nigeria with international best practices.

The 2023 general elections further demonstrated INEC's commitment to innovation, particularly through the deployment of the Bimodal Voter Accreditation System (BVAS) and the INEC Results Viewing (IReV) portal. These technologies were designed to improve voter accreditation and ensure the real-time electronic transmission of results. Yet, despite these advancements, the elections were not without controversy. Many Nigerians questioned the credibility of the process, raising concerns about technical failures, logistical challenges, and perceived irregularities in result collation. This skepticism fueled debates about the legitimacy of the eventual winner, Bola Ahmed Tinubu, and highlighted the enduring challenges of electoral governance in Nigeria.

The legitimacy of the Tinubu presidency is further complicated by the "winner-takes-all" character of Nigerian politics, which excludes losing candidates and their supporters from meaningful participation in governance. This exclusion exacerbates ethnic, regional, and religious divides, while also alienating the increasingly assertive youth population. Many young Nigerians, who had hoped for change, expressed dissatisfaction with the electoral outcome, with social media amplifying their grievances through trending hashtags such as *#RevolutionNow* following INEC's declaration of Tinubu as president (Sahara Reporters, 2023a). The widespread frustration has also been reflected in the rising wave of emigration among youths seeking better opportunities abroad, often through perilous routes across the Sahara Desert and Mediterranean Sea.

Scholars have argued that the legitimacy crisis confronting Tinubu's presidency can be traced to three interrelated factors. First, the flawed management of the 2023 elections by INEC and the judiciary weakened public confidence in the system. Second, Tinubu's personal reputation and political history raised doubts about his suitability for leadership among segments of the population. Third, the inability of Tinubu's party and political network to connect with citizens further alienated critical groups, particularly young voters. While Nigeria's electoral process has historically been marred by irregularities, the 2023 elections were viewed as both a step forward and a source of new tensions. On the one hand, local and international observers acknowledged progress in electoral management, particularly the use of digital technologies. On the other hand, unresolved challenges undermined the credibility of the outcome.

Against this backdrop, the relevance of e-governance in election management becomes clear. Through digitizing electoral processes, INEC has sought to address historical problems of fraud, ballot stuffing, and manipulation. The use of BVAS and IReV reflects a broader trend in Nigerian governance, where digital tools are increasingly employed to improve accountability and efficiency. Yet, as the 2023 elections demonstrate, technology alone cannot resolve the deeper structural issues of trust, legitimacy, and inclusivity in Nigeria's democracy.

In conclusion, the Nigerian case underscores the dual potential of e-governance: while it can enhance service delivery and strengthen electoral credibility, it also exposes the limits of technological fixes in the

absence of strong institutions, political will, and citizen trust. The study therefore situates the 2023 presidential elections in Rivers State within the broader discourse of e-governance, service delivery, and democratic legitimacy, highlighting both the opportunities and challenges that lie ahead for Nigeria's democratic future. Based on the above, this paper poses a question, thus: What is the impact of e-governance on voter participation in the 2023 presidential election in Rivers State?

THE DIFFUSION OF INNOVATION THEORY AND ELECTORAL GOVERNANCE IN NIGERIA

The Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DOI), developed by Everett Rogers, has long provided a useful framework for understanding how new technologies and ideas are adopted across societies and organizations. Originally rooted in agricultural studies of hybrid corn adoption in Iowa during the 1930s (Ryan & Gross, 1943), Rogers' framework has since been applied across multiple disciplines, including political science, public health, education, communications, economics, and technology (Dooley, 1999; Stuart, 2000). At its core, DOI focuses on the perceived attributes of innovations, the decision-making processes surrounding their adoption, and the role of communication channels and social systems in determining their success.

According to Rogers (2003), five key attributes of innovations influence their likelihood of adoption: relative advantage, or the degree to which an innovation is seen as superior to existing practices; compatibility, or how well the innovation fits with established values and workflows; complexity, the perceived difficulty of understanding and using the innovation; trialability, the extent to which the innovation can be tested on a limited basis; and observability, the degree to which the results of the innovation are visible to others. The stronger these attributes are perceived, the faster the rate of adoption within a social system.

In addition, Rogers conceptualized an innovation-decision process, which involves five stages: knowledge, persuasion, decision, implementation, and confirmation. At the knowledge stage, individuals seek to understand what the innovation is and how it works. Persuasion and decision involve evaluating the innovation's potential benefits and risks, leading to either adoption or rejection. If adopted, the innovation is implemented, and its continued use is either confirmed or abandoned depending on the outcomes. Importantly, Rogers also acknowledged reinvention, whereby users adapt or modify innovations to better suit their local needs and contexts. This flexibility often determines whether an innovation sustains adoption over time.

Much diffusion research has concentrated on technological innovations, with Rogers (2003) using "technology" and "innovation" interchangeably. He described technology as a design for instrumental action that reduces uncertainty in cause-effect relationships to achieve desired outcomes. Each technology consists of hardware, the physical tool, and software, the informational base that guides its use. Innovations with limited observability, such as software systems, often experience slower adoption due to difficulties in clearly demonstrating their benefits.

Another critical element in DOI is uncertainty. Innovations inherently involve risk, as their consequences, whether desirable or undesirable, direct or indirect, anticipated or unanticipated are not always known in advance. Rogers (2003, p. 436) defined consequences as the changes that occur in an individual or social system as a result of adoption or rejection. To reduce uncertainty, effective communication becomes essential. Communication channels—whether interpersonal (two-way exchanges between individuals) or mass media (television, radio, newspapers) play a crucial role in shaping perceptions of innovations. Since diffusion is fundamentally a social process, trust and interpersonal networks are often more influential in determining adoption than abstract technical claims.

DOI also highlights the importance of social systems and adopter categories. Within any system, adopters fall into groups such as innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and laggards. Each group influences the diffusion process differently, creating tipping points where adoption accelerates. In electoral governance, these categories can map onto stakeholders such as election officials, political elites,

civil society actors, and ordinary voters, each with varying levels of willingness to embrace new technologies.

Applying DOI to electoral governance in Nigeria provides useful insights into both the potential and limitations of technological reforms such as the Bimodal Voter Accreditation System (BVAS) and the INEC Results Viewing (IREV) portal. INEC's adoption of these innovations aligns with Rogers' principles: BVAS promised relative advantage by replacing error-prone manual processes with biometric verification; it was moderately compatible with existing electoral workflows; its complexity required extensive voter and staff training; its trialability was limited due to nationwide deployment; and its observability was high, as both successes and failures were widely reported. These mixed attributes help explain the uneven outcomes of BVAS during the 2023 general elections.

While BVAS was lauded for enhancing transparency, numerous cases of malfunction, delayed accreditation, and attempted cyberattacks on IREV underscored the persistent uncertainty surrounding electoral technologies. As DOI predicts, when uncertainty is not sufficiently reduced through effective communication, training, and institutional support adoption can falter, leading to public skepticism. Many Nigerians perceived the 2023 elections as flawed, not because innovations were absent, but because their implementation was inconsistent and easily manipulated within weak institutional structures.

Here, DOI intersects with the broader question of institutional capacity and legitimacy. Although INEC possesses vast constitutional powers to deliver credible elections, in practice it struggles with weak independence, susceptibility to political interference, and limited accountability. According to Rogers' framework, innovations cannot succeed if the social system adopting them lacks coherence and trust. In Nigeria, elites frequently exploit electoral bodies as instruments for seizing power rather than strengthening democracy. Lessons from past elections are rarely institutionalized, meaning innovations are often adopted in form but not in substance.

The legitimacy crisis surrounding Bola Ahmed Tinubu's presidency after the 2023 elections illustrates this dynamic. Despite the deployment of new technologies, many Nigerians, especially youths rejected the electoral outcome, trending hashtags like *#RevolutionNow* (Sahara Reporters, 2023) and expressing their disillusionment through increased emigration. According to DOI, innovations must not only be technically effective but also socially accepted. In Nigeria, technological reforms have struggled to gain legitimacy because the wider political culture remains dominated by corruption, patronage, and "winner-takes-all" politics that exclude opposition voices.

Furthermore, DOI underscores the importance of confirmation, the stage where adopters evaluate whether their decision to use an innovation was correct. For Nigerian voters, the experience of BVAS and IREV during the 2023 elections provided little confirmation of positive outcomes. Instead, failures in result transmission, allegations of manipulation, and judicial compromises reinforced skepticism. Thus, innovations that were intended to reduce uncertainty ironically increased it, undermining public trust.

Other institutions meant to check electoral abuses, such as the judiciary and legislature, have themselves been compromised by state capture. The judiciary's perceived lack of impartiality in adjudicating election disputes and the legislature's role as a rubber stamp erode citizens' faith in governance. As Rogers noted, adoption of innovations is inseparable from the credibility of the social system that promotes them. When institutions are weak, innovations cannot achieve their intended impact.

In conclusion, the Diffusion of Innovation Theory offers a valuable lens for analyzing electoral governance in Nigeria. It shows that while technological tools like BVAS and IREV possess attributes that can enhance transparency and efficiency, their success depends on reducing uncertainty through effective communication, building institutional capacity, and fostering legitimacy. Without these conditions, innovations risk being rejected or reinvented in ways that perpetuate, rather than resolve, democratic deficits. Ultimately, Nigeria's electoral challenges demonstrate that innovation alone cannot substitute for strong, independent institutions and genuine political commitment to democratic principles.

METHODOLOGY

This paper adopted a mixed-methods design, specifically a triangulation approach, which integrated both qualitative and quantitative techniques. The qualitative strand relied on structured interviews, while the quantitative strand utilized questionnaires, complemented by secondary materials including textbooks, scholarly journals, reports, and credible online sources. This choice of design aligns with contemporary research affirming that mixed methods enhance both reliability and validity by converging data from multiple sources (Joshua & Fasinu, 2023).

The population comprised 3,547,997 residents across nine Local Government Areas (LGAs) within the three senatorial districts of Rivers State (National Bureau for Statistics [NBS], 2022). The sample size was calculated using Taro Yamane’s formula with a 5% margin of error, a method still widely applied in recent studies. Simple random sampling guided the distribution of questionnaires, while 25 key informants were purposively selected for interviews. These informants represented four categories: INEC officials, civil society actors, registered voters, and members of the public, chosen for their expertise and relevant experiences.

Data collection employed two instruments: structured questionnaires and interview guides. The questionnaires contained closed-ended items directly linked to the study objectives, whereas the interviews offered depth and contextual understanding. To strengthen findings, primary data were cross-validated with secondary sources. The credibility of the instruments was ensured through expert reviews, adviser input, and a pilot test, which established both content and face validity. Reliability was confirmed through expert scoring, yielding over 90% agreement among evaluators.

For analysis, data were organized into frequency tables and expressed in simple percentages. Responses were grouped and compared to determine patterns of agreement, which formed the basis for interpretations and conclusions.

PRESENTATION OF DATA

This section presents and analyzes the data obtained from the administered questionnaires and interviews. The first part focuses on the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents, while the second part examines their responses to the core issues raised by the study. Data were analyzed using simple percentage methods, and findings are discussed accordingly.

Table 1: Response Rate of Administered Questionnaires

Administration of Questionnaires	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Number of questionnaires administered	400	100
Number of questionnaires not returned	30	7
Number of questionnaires retrieved	370	93
Number of questionnaires valid for the study	370	93

Source: Field Work, 2025

As shown in Table 1, of the 400 questionnaires distributed, 370 (93%) were completed and retrieved, while 30 (7%) were not returned. With a response rate of 93%, the study achieved a highly satisfactory level of participation, which strengthens the reliability of the findings.

Table 2: Distribution and Retrieval of Questionnaires by Category

Category	Distributed	Returned	Percentage (%)
INEC	100	95	26
CSOs/NGOs	100	97	26
Voters	100	96	26
Public	100	82	22
Total	400	370	100

Source: Field Work, 2025